

COMPOSITE BONDED REPAIR OF CRACKED PANELS SUBJECT TO ACOUSTIC FATIGUE

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SUMMARY: The skin of an aircraft can vibrate as a result of pressure waves caused by engine and/or aerodynamic effects. In modern fighter aircraft such as the F/A-18, sound pressure levels have been recorded up to 170dB over the surface of the skin. In the F/A-18 cracking has occurred in the lower nacelle, typically along the boundaries of the panel. These cracks often originate from a fastener line and grow along the boundary and then turn into the centre of the panel. In the case of the F/A-18, cracking was due to higher than expected pressure levels caused by an aerodynamic disturbance at the inlet lip. Attempts have been made to repair these panels with boron fibre patches, however the cracks have continued to grow. This paper aims at attempting to understand the mechanism's of cracking of the panels subjected to acoustic excitation and the influence of bonded repairs.

KEYWORDS: bonded repair, random response, acoustic fatigue

INTRODUCTION

Acoustic fatigue is due to a very high intensity excitation as a result of pressure waves caused by either engine/or aerodynamic effects. Acoustically-induced cracking has occurred on the external surface of the lower nacelle skin on the F/A-18, illustrated in Fig. 1. In these regions overall sound pressure levels (OASPL) greater than 170 dB have been measured in flight. These high sound pressure levels appear to be a result of an aerodynamic disturbance at the inlet lip [1]. Typical cracks occur along a line of rivets or run parallel to the rivet line and may turn into the centre of the panel, as shown in the inset. Cracking generally occurs along the longer side of the panel where the bending stresses due to out of plane vibrations are a maximum. Up to a third of the F/A-18's in the RAAF fleet are effected by these cracks.

The standard repair for such cracking is to remove and replace the panel. The standard long term fix is to incorporate additional stiffeners on the inside to stiffen the panel. This has two effects firstly to reduce the panels response, i.e. lower stress, for a given load and secondly it increases the resonant frequencies of the panel to frequencies well outside the recorded excitation frequencies.

In order to reduce cost of repairing such cracked structures a bonded repair would be preferred. Such a repair was designed and implemented on an existing cracked aircraft. The benefits of such a repair are reflected in the time required to carry out the repair; typically 60 hours for the mechanical repair and approximately 15-25 hours for the bonded repair. While in the past boron fibre patches have been used as a cost effective means of repairing cracked aircraft structures, in this case however, the cracks continued to grow.

The work reported here will involve the estimation of the root mean square (r.m.s.) response of the stress intensity factor (K) in the cracked and cracked/repaired cases as an attempt to understand the problems involved in patching cracks in such an environment.

Fig. 1: Location of the cracking in the lower nacelle inlet.

THEORY

Random Response Analysis

The random response analysis capability of the NASTRAN program has been used to solve this problem [2]. This involves a solution in the frequency domain after the transfer function, $H(\omega)$, is generated. Together with the power spectral density (PSD) of the excitation, $S_i(\omega)$, the PSD of the response, $S_j(\omega)$, is determined:

$$S_j(\omega) = |H(\omega)|^2 S_i(\omega) \quad (1)$$

This analysis allows the statistical properties of the system to be evaluated. Random vibrations involve all frequencies at any one instant in time. After calculating the PSD, the root mean square (r.m.s.) of the response can be determined by computing the square root of the PSD area:

$$j_{rms} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{\infty} S_j(\omega) d\omega} \quad (2)$$

A similar application of finite element techniques to undertake a PSD analysis to acoustic fatigue problems has been reviewed by Climent and Casalengua [3].

Stress Intensity Factors

In the F.E. model the depth of the plate is modelled using a single layer of 20 noded brick elements, and as such will model bending behaviour of the skin. The skin thickness is approximately 1 mm , hence the condition of plane stress is assumed. The computation of the stress intensity factor may be determined directly from the crack tip element used around the crack tip or from displacements using a crack opening (COD) formula. The r.m.s. crack tip stress intensity factors for mode I and III are derived from the standard asymptotic relations:

$$K_{I rms} = \frac{E V_{rms}}{4} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{l}} \quad (3)$$

$$K_{III rms} = G W_{rms} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{l}} \quad (4)$$

where E = Young's modulus

G = Shear modulus

V_{rms} = mode I crack opening r.m.s. displacement

W_{rms} = mode III crack opening r.m.s. displacement

l = length of the crack tip element

FEA METHODOLOGY VALIDATION

The complexity of the random response analysis and number of assumptions made is such that validation of the analysis was necessary. Both experimental and analytical work has been carried out by Byrnes [4]. In this case the plate used is that shown in Fig.2 and the PSD of the acoustic excitation is given in Fig. 3. Dimensions of the plate are $B=500 \text{ mm}$, $C=166 \text{ mm}$ and thickness= 1.2 mm with a crack of length A . This plate was clamped along edges except one edge, which was partially restrained. The unrestrained region represented a crack along one side. The length of the crack has been expressed as a ratio A/B . Material properties of the aluminium plate are given in Table 1, with the structural damping coefficient set to 0.055. R.m.s. strains were measured at a point 25 mm ahead of the crack tip, the results are reproduced in Fig. 4 along with an analytical solution also developed by Byrnes [4].

The F.E. results are also shown in Fig.4. Only three experimental data points were published in [4], and in each case the F.E. results are within 10%. However disagreement does exist with the analytical solution for crack length to plate width ratios below 0.4 . It is not clear why this difference occurs. The analytical solution is based on contributions from the first and second mode shapes only. However the F.E. PSD of the response allows for many mode shapes.

Fig. 2: Geometry of plate used for the validation of the analysis.

Fig. 3: Power Spectral Density of the pressure excitation used in [4]. results.

Fig. 4: Comparison of F.E., experimental and analytic results.

FEA OF CRACKED NACELLE INLET

A simplified model has been developed in which the skin is considered to be flat. However, to take account of all shear deformation the structure has been idealised as a fully three-dimensional structure using 20 noded brick elements. The geometry of the structure is shown in Fig. 5. The mesh size of the skin structure is 75x60 elements, while the patch and skin is 40x40 elements. As shown, the patch only extends partially across the panel. Sufficient elements have been used to define the minimum crack length considered. Material properties for the skin, adhesive and boron are shown in Table 1. For the analysis presented here, it is assumed that the boron patch is isotropic. The main reason that 20 noded bricks were used in the skin is that calculations for K can be made corresponding to a bending field. Also, the behaviour of the adhesive has been modelled as a 3 dimensional element, to allow for shear deformation and damping in a future study. A structural damping coefficient of 0.032 has been used [1].

Fig. 5: Dimensions of F/A-18 nacelle inlet panel

The boundary conditions for this model are considered to fully clamped except for the crack region which is not restrained. The patch above the crack also remains fully constrained. Clearly crack closure will occur at an increasing distance away from the crack tip, however the complexity in introducing such constraints has not been included in this preliminary study.

Table 1: Material properties.

Material	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Density (Mg/mm ²)
Aluminium	70000.	.33	2.77x10 ⁻⁹
Adhesive	2273.	.35	1.2x10 ⁻⁹
Boron	207000.	.33	2.0x10 ⁻⁹

Flight measurements, Ref. 1, have been made of the one third octave band sound pressure level using microphones located at the nacelle inlet area, and this result is shown in Fig. 6. The spectrum level, relative to the overall sound pressure level (OASPL), is derived from this result and is also shown in Fig. 6. This spectrum is now used as the excitation pressure on the FE model described above.

Fig. 6: Maximum sound pressure level and spectrum over nacelle inlet.

The relationship between the spectrum sound pressure level (SPL) and the r.m.s. fluctuating pressure (p) is given in [3] as:

$$p_{rms} = 10^{(SPL/20 - 4.69897)} \quad (3)$$

and the power spectral density of acoustic pressure, i.e. PSD of the excitation, at any given frequency is given by:

$$PSD = p_{rms}^2 = 10^{(SPL/10 - 9.3979)} \quad (4)$$

The curve in Fig. 6 has been approximated with the three points shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Input power spectral density

Frequency (hz)	Pressure spectrum level in dB	R.M.S. pressure level ,(MPa) ² /hz
31.5	140	4.0 x10 ⁻⁸
1000	137	2.005x10 ⁻⁸
8000	124.1	1.028x10 ⁻⁹

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Shown in Fig. 7 are the natural frequencies versus crack length for the cracked and un-repaired panel and also the repaired panel for the first 3 mode shapes. In the case of the cracked un-repaired structure, increasing the crack length significantly reduces the natural frequency of the panel. Also as expected, repaired panels have little variation in natural frequency with crack length. Furthermore the repaired panels have substantially higher natural frequencies for all modes than the un-repaired panels. The boron repair has a definite influence on the panel stiffness.

Fig. 7 : Frequency versus crack length for un-repaired and repaired cases.

Mode shapes have been computed corresponding to a short and long crack length for the repaired panel. The first 3 mode shapes for a short crack length (100 mm) which is covered by the patch, is shown in Fig. 8. Clearly the crack tip behaviour is dominated by the mode I stress intensity factor K_I , arising from bending that would occur under excitation of these modes. The mode shape corresponding to a long crack (196 mm) that extends outside the patch is shown in Fig. 9. In this case the unsupported crack has a mode shape that when excited under these modes will also give rise to the mode III stress intensity factor K_{III} .

The modal analysis indicates that both the mode I and III stress intensity factors will be significant. The mode I stress intensity factor K_I for the cracked un-repaired panel is shown in Fig. 10a. As expected, the general response is an increase of K_I with crack length. The left hand crack tip is always closer to the clamped edge of the panel than the right hand crack tip, and since the bending stresses are a maximum midway along the boundary, the right hand tip gives the highest value of K_I . The values of K_I , in relation to the fracture toughness, are significant and explain crack growth.

In the repaired panel the neutral axis is offset and as a result K_I is evaluated at both inner and outer surfaces of the skin, the repair being applied to the outer surface. Being a one sided repair the repair is more effective on the outer surface which is more closely restrained [6].

These bending effects are clearly shown in Fig. 10b. The right hand crack results in the highest values for K_I located on the inner surface. These values of K_I are significantly high before the crack grows out from under the patch, and explains continued crack growth. For a normal 'static' repair in which the only significant events are manoeuvre loads and gust loads the repair would be successful. However in the environment of acoustic fatigue at a frequency of 300 Hz the repair will not be effective

Fig. 8 : Mode shapes for short crack (repaired).

The mode III stress intensity factor K_{III} for the cracked un-repaired panel is shown in Fig.11a. The values of K_{III} increase with crack length significantly for both left and right hand crack tips, and the numerical value of K_{III} is greater than K_I . Clearly K_{III} will contribute significantly to crack growth. In the case of the repaired panel, shown in Fig. 11b, the values K_{III} for a crack not growing outside the patch, are low, but not zero. However, once the crack grows outside the patch (i.e. for crack lengths > 120 mm) K_{III} increases significantly.

Fig. 9 : Mode shapes for long crack (repaired).

Fig. 10: (a) Stress intensity factor K_I in un-repaired panel for left and right hand crack tips. (b) Stress intensity factor K_I in repaired panel. (Note the change in scale.)

Fig. 11: (a) Stress intensity factor K_{III} for un-repaired panel. (b) Stress intensity factor K_{III} for repaired panel.

Fig. 12: PSD of displacement ($\propto K_I$) and running integral of the PSD for repaired panel of crack length (a) $2a=96$ mm, (b) $2a=196$ mm and (c) un-repaired panel with crack length $2a=196$ mm. PSD of displacement ($\propto K_{III}$) and running integral of the PSD for (d) repaired panel of crack length $2a=196$ mm and (e) un-repaired panel of crack length $2a=196$ mm.

For a crack length of $2a=96$ mm, the PSD of the response is proportional to the mode I stress intensity factor, and is shown in Fig. 12a. This corresponds to some of the mode shapes shown in Fig. 7. The peak response occurs at a frequency of 291 Hz and corresponds to mode shape 1 in Fig. 7. With increasing frequency the peaks correspond sequentially to the higher modes. The contribution of the modes to the response can be determined by a running integral of the response and is shown in Fig. 12a. These results indicate that about 98% of the response is due to mode 1.

In the case of the repaired panel containing a long crack of 196 mm the response for K_I is shown in Fig. 12b. It is evident from the running integral that mode 1 makes the major contribution to this response followed by modes 4 and 5. However the response for K_{III} ,

shown in Fig. 12d, clearly shows that mode 6 makes the major contribution at a frequency of 933 Hz, followed by mode 1.

In the case of long cracks in the un-repaired panel, the response for K_I and K_{III} is shown in Figs. 12c and 12e, respectively. In this case mode 1 makes the major contribution to these factors.

CONCLUSIONS

Validation of the PSD method has been achieved from both experimental data and analytical formula.

The analysis carried out here has simulated and characterised the growth of the crack in the cracked and repaired panel. It has been found that after patching a significantly high mode I stress intensity factor K_I exists on the inner surface of the right hand crack tip likely to promote crack growth.

For a short crack length in the repaired structure, a running integral of the PSD of the displacement, ($\propto K_I$) has shown that mode shape 1 contributes about 98% of the response at the crack tip. In the case of a long crack in the repaired panel, the running integral showed that mode 6 provided the major contribution to the response for K_{III} . For all other cases considered mode 1 provided the major contribution to K_I and K_{III} .

For the un-repaired panel it is expected that both K_I and K_{III} will have a significant contribution to crack growth.

FUTURE INVESTIGATIONS

The use of thicker patches which extend across the complete panel.

The use of constrained layer damping in a thick adhesive layer.

The trade-off between uni-directional and quasi - isotropic patches.

The application of patches to un-cracked panels to prevent initiation of cracks.

REFERENCES

1. A/B/C/D Aircraft Lower Nacelle Skin Acoustic and Strain Measurements and Sonic Fatigue Analysis. MDC 94B0044. Mar,1994.
2. Blakely MSC/NASTRAN, basic dynamics analysis, user's guide. The MacNeal-Schwendler Corporation, Dec,1993.
3. H. Climent and J. Casalengua. Application of a PSD technique to acoustic fatigue Stress Calculations in Complex Structures. Symposium on ' Impact of Acoustic Loads on Aircraft Structures', Lillehammer, Norway, May 1994.
4. K.P. Byrne Strains Affecting the Growth Rate of Edge Cracks in Acoustically Excited Panels. ISVR Tech. Rep. 59, Nov, 1972.
5. The estimation of r.m.s stress in stiffened skin panels subjected to random acoustic loading. Engineering Sciences Data Unit Number 72005. July, 1984.
6. R.J. Callinan, L.R.F. Rose and C.H. Wang. Three Dimensional Stress Analysis of Crack Patching. To be presented at ICF9 in June, 1997.